

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ORGANIC-BASED ADMIXED INHIBITORS IN MULTI-EXPOSURE ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: Reinforced concrete cement (RCC) is the most widely used construction material today. However, its durability remains a critical concern, primarily due to the issue of reinforcement corrosion. Corrosion in steel reinforcements weakens RCC structures over time, ultimately leading to structural failure. This process is often triggered by environmental factors such as chloride ions and carbon dioxide, which contribute to the degradation of the embedded steel. As corrosion progresses, rust forms on the steel surface, occupying a greater volume than the original metal. This expansion generates tensile and flexural stresses, causing cracks, spalling, and delamination in the concrete. One of the most effective and commonly used preventive measures against corrosion is the application of corrosion inhibitors, which are easy to incorporate into concrete mixtures. This study focuses on evaluating the performance of two organic inhibitors—4-amino benzoic acid (ABA) and triethyl phosphate (TEP)—when added to concrete exposed to chloride ingress and carbonation environments. Initially, both inhibitors were tested in a simulated pore solution representing the concrete environment. Subsequently, concrete prisms made from Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) and Portland Pozzolana Cement (PPC) were cast, and the corrosion inhibition performance of the compounds was assessed using two electrochemical techniques: Linear Polarization Resistance (LPR) and Half-Cell Potential (HCP) measurements. Additionally, concrete cubes were prepared to analyze free chloride content and carbonation depth. Experimental findings revealed that ABA effectively inhibited corrosion in PPC concrete by acting as a chelating agent, forming a passive protective layer that prevented further deterioration. Similar results were observed in the pore solution test. In contrast, while TEP showed promising performance in the pore solution, it failed to provide corrosion protection in concrete exposed to chloride ingress and carbonation. This was attributed to its single functional group and insufficient dosage in the concrete mix. The results of free chloride content and carbonation depth analysis further supported the findings from the prismatic concrete specimens, confirming the superior performance of ABA over TEP in mitigating reinforcement corrosion.

Keywords: Corrosion, Durability, Organic Inhibitors, Concrete, 4-Amino Benzoic Acid, Triethyl Phosphate, Corrosion Mechanism, Reinforcement Protection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete, composed of aggregates, cement, and water, is the most widely used material in construction, employed in buildings, bridges, tunnels, and other infrastructure projects. While concrete is strong under compression, it is weak in tension, which is why steel reinforcement is commonly used to strengthen these structures. Reinforced concrete is known for its durability

and cost-effectiveness, often providing a long service life with minimal maintenance. However, the rising levels of environmental pollutants, particularly chloride ions and greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide (CO₂), have accelerated the corrosion of steel reinforcement, posing a significant challenge. This corrosion process reduces the lifespan of reinforced concrete structures and increases maintenance costs due to issues like spalling and delamination.

Corrosion in reinforced concrete has far-reaching economic and social implications, threatening the safety of workers in various industries and significantly impacting global economies. It is estimated that the global cost of corrosion exceeds 3% of the world's GDP (Source: Inspectioneering). In India, where economic stability is crucial, corrosion costs approximately USD 40 billion annually, around 4% of the country's GDP, affecting infrastructure, industrial machinery, and even historical heritage (CII Corrosion Management Committee). To ensure the longevity of reinforced concrete structures, the quality of concrete should be evaluated not only for strength and workability but also for durability. Protecting the embedded steel reinforcement is essential, and using corrosion inhibitors has emerged as one of the most effective strategies. This study focuses on evaluating the performance of organic corrosion inhibitors in mitigating reinforcement corrosion, particularly in environments where chloride ions penetrate the concrete and carbon dioxide is present in the surrounding atmosphere.

2. CAUSE OF CORROSION

The corrosion process occurring in reinforced steel bars is a significant challenge for concreted structures, impacting both their lifespan and economic viability. Therefore, understanding the factors that contribute to corrosion is crucial in the field of construction. Corrosion in steel primarily occurs due to two major types of attack on concrete:

- **Carbonation Attack**

Carbonation is a chemical process that occurs when carbonyl dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere reacts with the alkaline hydroxides present in concrete. When CO₂ dissolves in water, it forms a weak acid. This acid does not directly attack the cement paste but neutralizes the alkalis in the pore water, leading to the formation of calcium carbonate, which deposits on the pore surfaces. Figure 1.254 illustrates the process of carbonation-induced corrosion. Calcium hydroxide, presently in the concrete pores, dissolves in the pore water and helps maintain the pHs at its typical level of 12-13. However, when CO₂ reacts with calcium hydroxide in the concrete pores, it forms calcium carbonate, causing the pH to drop. Once the pH falls below a critical level, the protective passive layer on the steel is compromised, leading to corrosion. Carbonation-induced corrosion typically results in uniform corrosion across the structure.

Figure 1: Carbonation induced corrosion on concrete (Source : corrosion engineering)

- **Chloride Attack**

For the corrosion process to begin, chloride ions from the environment must penetrate the passive layer in concrete. These chloride ions act as catalysts, accelerating the anodic reaction at a much faster rate than usual, resulting in a higher rate of corrosion. This process significantly reduces the load-carrying capacity of the structure. Figure 1.3 illustrates chloride-induced

corrosion on the concrete surface. Unlike uniform corrosion, chloride-induced corrosion primarily causes pitting corrosion, which is localized and can severely weaken the structural integrity of reinforced concrete.

Figure 2: Chloride induced corrosion on concrete (Source: civil engineering forum)

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE WORK

Both organic and inorganic substances have previously been effectively employed as admixtures and migratory inhibitors in different environments of carbonation and chloride. Finding effective, affordable, and environmentally benign corrosion inhibitors is still a major task in the fight against corrosion. Therefore, the effectiveness of substances such as triethyl phosphate and 4-amino benzoic acid as inhibitors in a combined ingress chloride and carbonation environment is examined in this study. Additionally, the impact of several functional groups (amines, carboxyl, and phosphate) in a mixed environment is examined in reinforced concrete and pore solution.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several research studies have focused on the effectiveness of organic-based admixed inhibitors in multi-exposure environments.

Zheng et al. (2012) studied amino alcohol (AMA)-based organic inhibitors commonly used in commercial surface-applied corrosion protection. Concrete specimens (100×100×50 mm) with varying water/cement ratios were exposed to NaCl solutions for 30 days. The results showed that the inhibitor effectively blocked about 50% of chloride penetration in low water/cement ratio specimens by suppressing capillary absorption. However, as the water/cement ratio increased, the presence of macropores and capillaries reduced the inhibitor's effectiveness, weakening its pore-blocking ability and lowering chloride resistance at the same dosage.

Figure 3: Chloride profile of Group 1 specimen (Zheng et al. (2012))

Xu et al. (2016) examined the effectiveness of triethylenetetramine (TETA) as an organic corrosion inhibitor in chloride-contaminated concrete using bidirectional electromigration rehabilitation (BIEM). Their study found that TETA effectively inhibited corrosion in both carbonated and non-carbonated concrete. Electrochemical tests showed that a lower water-to-cement (w/c) ratio limited particle transfer due to increased alkalinity. While BIEM increased chloride concentration, electrochemical techniques (ECE) reduced porosity and improved passivation when applied sequentially.

Salthammer et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration between chemical and exposure scientists in assessing human exposure to chemicals in indoor environments. Their study highlighted the need for combined theoretical and experimental approaches to improve health risk evaluations.

Xie et al. (2018) developed a deep convolutional network model, MEFNet, to improve optical flow estimation under varying illumination. Their approach trained neural networks on multi-exposure image pairs, achieving high accuracy in HDR composition and flicker removal.

Teryusheva et al. (2020) analyzed the relationship between the molecular structure of organic compounds and their effectiveness as steel corrosion inhibitors. They identified key structural factors influencing cathodic and anodic processes and emphasized the importance of preventing microorganism resistance.

Shehnazdeep et al. (2022) reviewed corrosion inhibitors for mitigating chloride-induced corrosion in reinforced concrete. Their study covered both organic and inorganic inhibitors applied as admixtures or surface treatments and assessed their effects on mechanical properties.

Shaimaa et al. (2023) discussed corrosion processes, scaling, and experimental techniques for corrosion analysis. Their study explored the relationship between anticorrosion structures and their effectiveness, as well as emerging inhibitor technologies.

Alzamili et al. (2023) investigated multi-exposure image fusion (MEF) for high-dynamic-range (HDR) imaging, addressing ghost elimination in dynamic scenes. They identified challenges in existing MEF methods and proposed solutions for improving performance in dynamic environments.

- **Concluding Remarks**

Chemical compounds have long been utilized as corrosion inhibitors. The present literature review aids in understanding the mechanisms of various organic groups used as inhibitors,

ultimately contributing to cost and time savings. Amine-based inhibitors function by blocking pores, while carboxylic group inhibitors exhibit a steric effect. Phosphate-based inhibitors operate through adsorption mechanisms. Additionally, a combination of amine and carboxylic groups leads to the formation of complex compounds, as iron electrons bond with the unshared electron pairs of nitrogen and oxygen, enhancing corrosion protection.

6. FINDINGS

The efficiency of 4-amino benzoic acid (ABA) and triethyl phosphate (TEP) as admixed corrosion inhibitors in OPC and PPC concrete was evaluated. Concrete specimens were exposed to a chloride environment (0.035 g/cc in water) and a carbonation environment (5% CO₂) for two days each. Various experiments were conducted, leading to the following conclusions regarding the performance of ABA and TEP as corrosion inhibitors in ingress chloride and carbonation environments:

- Icorr values recorded at 24, 48, and 120 hours in pore solution indicated that both ABA and TEP exhibited corrosion inhibition effects. ABA performed more effectively at 0.1M concentration, as its carboxylic group acted as a chelating agent, enhancing its corrosion resistance. TEP also demonstrated inhibition due to its high phosphate content, which interacted with the steel rebar surface.
- Icorr values further revealed that 4-amino benzoic acid effectively inhibited corrosion in PPC concrete exposed to ingress chloride and carbonation environments. However, TEP did not exhibit significant inhibition, as its performance in both OPC and PPC concrete was similar to that of the control specimen. This was attributed to TEP's single functional group, which lacks chelating properties.
- Physical verification and mass loss measurements indicated that the percentage weight change was similar for all specimens, except for ABA in PPC concrete. This finding further validated the results obtained from half-cell potential (HCP) and Icorr measurements, confirming ABA's superior corrosion inhibition in PPC concrete.

REFERENCES

1. Han, J., Wang, K., Shi, J. and Wang, Y., 2012. Mechanism of triethanolamine on Portland cement hydration process and microstructure characteristics. *Construction and Building Materials*, 93, pp.457-462.
2. Rakanta, E., Zafeiropoulou, T. and Batis, G., 2013. Corrosion protection of steel with DMEA-based organic inhibitor. *Construction and Building Materials*, 44, pp.507-513.
3. Kaur, K., Goyal, S., Bhattacharjee, B. and Kumar, M., 2016. Efficiency of migratory-type organic corrosion inhibitors in carbonated environment. *Journal of advanced concrete technology*, 14(9), pp.548-558.
4. www.corrosionengineering.co.uk/knowledge-library/corrosion-of-steel-in-concrete
5. Salthammer, Tunga & Zhang, Yinping & Mo, Jinhan & Koch, Holger & Weschler, Charles. (2018). Assessing Human Exposure to Organic Pollutants in the Indoor Environment. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 57. 12228 – 12263. 10.1002/anie.201711023.
6. Xie, Zhifeng & Guo, Yu-Chen & Zhang, Shu-Han & Zhang, Wen-Jun & Ma, Lizhuang. (2018). Multi-Exposure Motion Estimation Based on Deep Convolutional Networks. *Journal of Computer Science and Technology*. 33. 487-501. 10.1007/s11390-018-1833-4.
7. Teryusheva, S.A.. (2020). Organic inhibitors of steel corrosion (analytical review of publications). *Practice of Anticorrosive Protection*. 25. 60-65. 10.31615/j.corros.prot.2020.96.2-7.

8. Shehnazdeep & Pradhan, Bulu. (2022). A study on effectiveness of inorganic and organic corrosion inhibitors on rebar corrosion in concrete: A review. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 65. 10.1016/j.matpr.2022.04.296.
9. Al-baghdadi, Shaimaa & Al-khazaali, Alaa & Al.Azawi, Khalida. (2023). A comprehensive review on the nature and synthetic organic compounds as corrosion inhibitors. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Innovation*. 07. 102-111. 10.36037/IJREI.2023.7302.
10. Alzamili, Zainab & Danach, Kassem & Frikha, Mondher. (2023). Concepts and Techniques of Multi-Exposure Image Fusion: A literature Review. *Design Engineering*.
11. wantarengineering
12. IS 456: 2000, "Indian Standard Code of Practice for Plain and Reinforced Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
13. IS 10262: 1982, "Recommended Guidelines for Concrete Mix design", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
14. IS 383: 1970, "Specification for Coarse aggregate and Fine aggregate from Natural Sources for Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
15. IS 9103: 1999, "Indian Standard Concrete Admixture Specification", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
16. IS 5816: 1999, "Splitting Tensile Strength of Concrete Method of Test", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
17. IS 9399: 1959, "Specification for Apparatus for Flexural Testing of Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
18. IS 516: 1959, "Flexural Strength of Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi